

FABRICATION AND MECHANICAL PROPERTIES OF MICRO-POROUS METAL COMPOSITES BY MIM-BASED POWDER SPACE HOLDER METHOD

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SUMMARY: A novel production method for the metal components with micro-sized porous structures has been developed by applying powder space holder (PSH) method to metal powder injection moulding (MIM) process. The representative materials are stainless steels, aluminium, copper, titanium, nickel and their alloy. This production method can comply with widespread applications with high functionality such as heat sinks, electrodes and medical implants and so on. Those applications welcome the advantages that this method proposed is capable of producing the micro-porous metal components with complicated shapes using most kinds of metal powder. The aim of this study is to clarify the effects of material combinations on the pore formation and some physical properties of sintered porous specimens. The green compacts were molded by uniaxial hot pressing for simplification using various porous compounds which were prepared with changing the combinations in size of metal powder and space holding particle, and were sintered at various temperatures. It was confirmed that the size of metal powder and space holding particle in addition to sintered temperature was main factors affecting significantly for the pore size, porosity, surface area and shrinkage of sintered porous specimens. Furthermore, the effective method to compensate the deficiencies on the mechanical property of porous metals was investigated in comparison with mechanical properties of the materials with homogeneous dense and porous structure. Co-sintering process was applied to form the graded porous structures after each porous compound was consolidated by sequential hot press moulding. The multilayer metals were obtained by changing the stacking sequence in co-sintering process. The skin layer and core were formed with high dense structure and micro-porous structure, respectively and conversely. It was confirmed that the method proposed was useful in producing the metal components with micro-sized porous and high functionally graded porous structures.

KEYWORDS: porous metal, metal injection moulding, space holder method, hot pressing, shrinkage, porosity, geometrical analysis, co-sintering, multilayer metals, bending property

INTRODUCTION

Porous metal materials including metal foams, cellular metals and metal sponges have been widely studied and used [1-4]. But they are new class of materials with low densities, large specific surface and novel properties in physically, mechanically, thermally, electrically and acoustically. Closed cell forms offer potential applications for light weight structures with sound and impact energy absorptions as structure elements. Open cell forms also poses high

functional applications such as heat exchangers and heat sinks as thermal managements, and medical implants, filters, electrodes as bio and chemical reaction. As the size of products decrease from meters to millimetres, the cell size tends to be small accordingly. However, no many studies deal with net-shape production of micro-porous metal components, which are strongly desired in higher functionally applications with cost efficient.

Fig. 1 shows the ranges of cell size and cell type against porosity for typical production methods of metal forms. These can be manufactured with commercial production methods, such as sintering of hollow sphere or metal textiles, melt gas injection in liquid metal, gas forming particle decomposition in semi-solid metal, vapour or electron-deposition method, entrapped gas expansion method and sintering of metal powders. Each method can be used with a small subset of methods to create porous materials with a limited range of cell size and porosity. In practical ways, it is very difficult for metals to produce with controlled dimensionally in a few or tens micrometers of cell size and selected arbitrarily both open and closed cell structures with specified porosity. At the moment, few methods can produce the net-shaped metal components with high production efficiency. Furthermore, the combination of highly dense and porous metals is promising for materials with a high specific modulus and high functionality. However it is not easy to control the cell size and its distribution in practice and much more so producing graded porous metals with complicated shapes.

Metal injection moulding (MIM) is, on the other hand, a manufacturing method combining the traditional powder metallurgy process and plastic injection moulding. It has over the past decade established itself as a comparative manufacturing process for small precision components which would be costly to produce by alternative methods. It is capable of producing for comparatively small parts with complex shapes from almost all types of materials including metals, ceramics, inter-metallic compounds, and composites [5-7].

Fig. 1: Cell size against porosity for typical production methods of porous metals: (a)Metal textiles, (b)Investment casting, (c)Constructed metal lattices, (d)Melt gas injection in liquid metal, (e)Vapour or electro-deposition of metal on open cell polymer foam template, (f)Liquid metal solidification or powder coating of polymer foam template mold, (g)Gas forming particle decomposition in melt, (h)Gas forming particle decomposition in semi solid metal, (i)Hollow sphere, (j)Gas metal eutectic solidification, (k)Entrapped gas expansion

Recently MIM has been studied not only for hard metals, but also for materials such as titanium, copper and aluminium [8, 9]. Unlike in the case of powder metallurgy, MIM requires the mixing of metal powder and polymeric binder and solvent extract or pyrolysis of organic constituents in debinding step, which are characterized as unique process of MIM. Then we should make the better use of these processes, which does not have a little segregation. This is one of reasonable points why we have developed the production method for micro-porous metal components based on MIM process. Authors have contrived producing metal components with micro-sized porous structure by applying powder space holder (PSH) method to MIM process [9-12].

In this study, micro-porous metal components were produced by PSH method developed based on MIM process, and the effects of material combination and sintering conditions on the pore formation and some physical properties of sintered porous specimens were investigated. Also, the feasibility of producing the graded porous structure was demonstrated by co-sintering process to show the effectiveness for compensating the deficiencies on the mechanical property of porous structures.

PRODUCTION OF MICRO-POROUS METALS

Concept of MIM-based Powder Space Holder Method

The concept of production method for micro-porous metals we developed based on MIM process is illustrated in Fig. 2. In a conventional MIM process, the feedstock materials are composed of metal powder and binders, and a high densification after debinding and sintering processes is very important for high quality MIM products. In highly porous structured MIM products, on the other hand, many spaces require retention after sintering. We have therefore applied PSH method into MIM process. In addition to metal powder and thermoplastic binders, coarse spherical materials made of thermoplastics were used as lost material for formation of fine porous structures in MIM components. Material combination of space holding particle and metal powder in addition to sintering conditions determines principally the porous structure.

This production method has widespread applications such as heat sinks, electrodes and medical implants and so on. Those applications welcome the advantages that this proposed method is a net-shaped production for micro-porous metal components with 3 dimensional complicated shapes and high functionally graded structures and can be applied to most kinds of metal powder, such as stainless steels, aluminium, copper, titanium, nickel and their alloy as the representative materials.

Fig. 2: Powder space holder method for producing micro-porous metals

EXPERIMENTAL DETAILS

Experimental Materials and Porous Compounds

The experimental materials used for porous compounds are listed in Table 1. The metal powders are austenitic stainless steel, 316L produced by water-atomization method. The binder is from the polyacetal family. Spherical particles (10 μ m or 50 μ m in mean diameter) made of polymethylmethacrylate (PMMA) were used for holding the space. These materials were co-mixed and pelletized with high-pressure kneader and plunger-type extruder. The resultant specimen ID's are named as 3-10 or 3-50 in 10 μ m or 50 μ m of PMMA particle used for 3 μ m of 316L powder, and 9-50 in 50 μ m of PMMA particle used for 9 μ m of 316L powder. The fraction of PMMA particles was varied from 0 to 80vol.% as main experimental parameter.

Table 1: Experimental materials and fraction of constituents

	Compositions	Supplier, Product ID	Mean diameter	Volume fraction	
				MIM feedstock	Porous compound
Metal powder	Stainless steel, 316L	Atmix Co., Ltd., PF-2F	3 μ m	50vol.%	20-100vol.%
		Atmix Co., Ltd., PF-20J	9 μ m		
Binder	Wax, Polyacetal	-----	-----	50vol.%	
Space holding particle	Poly-methylmethacrylate (PMMA)	Soken Chemical Co., LTD., MX-1000	10 μ m	-----	0-80vol.%
		Ganz Chemical Co., LTD., GM-5003	50 μ m		

Preparation Conditions and Evaluation Method

Using various porous compounds, the circular shape of green compacts (40mm diameter, 2mm thick) were prepared by hot press moulding for simplicity of this experiments, but can be also produced by injection moulding [9,10,12]. The hot press moulding was carried out under constant conditions where die temperature and gage pressure was 200°C and 10MPa, respectively. The debinding and sintering were sequentially processed at 600°C for 2hr in N₂ and at 1050-1200°C for 2hr in Ar gas atmospheres in the vacuum furnace to avoid oxidizing. Fig. 3 shows the production process of multilayered metals with graded porous structures, which were demonstrated by co-sintering process [8, 11]. The circular shape of the green compacts was prepared by hot press moulding in this study, but can be produced with injection moulding using dense MIM feedstock and porous compounds with various contents of space holding particles.

Fig. 3: Production process of multilayered metals with graded porous structures

The relative density, i.e. reciprocal of porosity, of sintered specimens was measured with micrometer calliper and analytical balance. The pore size was measured with porometer (PMI, CPF-1100-AXLSP). Surface structure was observed by SEM and the sintered specimens were performed 3 points bending test and recorded the images under loading by digital microscope.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

Surface structures

The microstructures on the surface of sintered specimens which were produced using various porous compounds are shown in Fig. 4. Number of pores on the surface visually increases as the fraction of PMMA particles increases from 0 to 80vol.%, and the pore size is significantly dependent of diameter of PMMA particles. These characteristics are typical pore formation behaviour of PSH method. To make micro-sized porous stainless steel with much higher surface-to-volume ratio, it is better to take the porous compounds with combination of 3 μ m 316L powder and 10 μ m PMMA particle.

Fig. 4: Surface of specimens with various sizes of metal powder and PMMA particle

Sintered shrinkage and Porosity

Fig. 5 shows the shrinkage and porosity of sintered porous specimens with various fractions of PMMA particle. The specimens 3-10 and 9-50 were sintered at 1050°C and 1200°C, respectively. In both specimens, the shrinkage holds at constant up to around 50-60vol.% of PMMA particle and increases significantly as further increasing in fraction of PMMA particle. It is considered that the transition point is corresponded nearly to changing of closed to open cell structures. In other words, shrinking percentage stays constant in the closed cell structure despite of fraction of PMMA particle, and increases according to the fraction of PMMA particle in open cell structure. Then the definite transition points are shown at boundary between the closed cell structure and open cell structure. Also, the porosity of both specimens increase in proportion to fraction of PMMA particles, and the transition of porosity are appeared as well as the results of shrinkage.

The pore size and specific surface area of sintered specimens with variant sizes of PMMA particle are listed in Table 2. As PMMA particle size decreases, the narrowest diameter of pore decreases accordingly, but specific surface area increases significantly. As the result, narrowest diameter of pore was approximately equal to a fifths part of PMMA particle.

(a) Shrinkage in diameter

(b) Porosity

Fig. 5: Shrinkage and porosity as function of fraction of space holding particle

Table 2: Pore size and surface area of porous specimens with variant space holding particles

Mean diameter of PMMA particle	Narrowest diameter of pore	Specific surface area
50 μm	9.62 μm	0.02 m^2/g
10 μm	2.06 μm	0.19 m^2/g

Effects of sintering temperature

Fig. 6 shows the shrinkage and porosity of porous specimens with 60vol.% PMMA particles, which were sintered at various temperatures. It was confirmed from these graphs that the shrinkage increased, and the porosity decreased accordingly in any specimens as sintering temperature increased. These phenomena can be also confirmed from the evidences that the pore size tends to reduce with an excess sintering in any specimens. The shrinkage in diameter is ideally 20% which is calculated by solid loading of MIM feedstock, i.e. 50vol.%. Therefore, when the sintering temperature are set at 1050 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ for 3 μm 316L-10 μm PMMA (Specimen 3-10), 1200 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ for 3 μm 316L-50 μm PMMA (Specimen 3-50), and 1300 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ for 9 μm 316L-50 μm PMMA (Specimen 9-50), the shrinkage is closer to 20%, then the porosity could be achieved as close as the adding content of PMMA particle, i.e. 60vol.%.

(a) Shrinkage in diameter

(b) Porosity

Fig. 6: Shrinkage and porosity as function of sintering temperature (60vol.% PMMA)

Then it is concluded that porous structures formed soundly with similarly sized pores can be obtained under the above-cited sintering conditions for each combination in sizes of metal powder and space holding particle. Furthermore, it is revealed that the sintering is more active in finer metal powder and at higher temperature, and small pores exist additionally between metal particles by insufficient sintering in 50 μ m PMMA specimens (specimens 3-50 and 9-50), while cellular pore resulting from space holding particle affects remarkably by sintering temperature in 10 μ m PMMA specimen (specimen 3-10).

Geometrical analysis

The transition points in fraction of PMMA particle, which means a boundary of closed cell structure and open cell structure, were estimated by simple geometrical analysis. When assuming that the metal powders are uniformly located around a PMMA particle, it can be modelled as a spherical PMMA particle coated by single layer of metal powder. When the spheres are closed-packed in face centred cubic (fcc) structure, the volumetric fraction of PMMA particle reaches maximum in closed pore structure. The maximum fraction of PMMA particle, $(V_{PMMA})_{max}$, is derived from Eqn. 1 as follows:

$$(V_{PMMA})_{max} = \frac{4 \times \frac{4}{3} \pi \left(\frac{d_p}{2} \right)^3}{\left\{ \sqrt{2} (d_p + d_m) \right\}^3} \quad (1)$$

Where, d_p is mean diameter of PMMA particle, d_m is mean diameter of 316L powder.

The maximum fractions of PMMA particle under closed cell structure were estimated by the geometrical analysis, and they can be compared to the transition points in fraction of PMMA particle, which were obtained from the experimental results, i.e. the shrinkage percentage and the porosity for specimens with various size ratios of particle shown in Fig.5 (a) and (b), respectively. The fractions of PMMA particle in these transition points were plotted for several ratios of particle size as shown in Fig. 7. For comparison, the maximum fraction of PMMA particle estimated by Eqn. 1 is drawn with the curve in Fig. 7. The curve means a boundary of closed cell and open cell structure. It was revealed that the experimental results agreed well with the curve estimated by geometrical analysis.

Fig. 7: Size ratio of PMMA particle/Metal powder versus maximum fraction of PMMA particle under closed cell structure

Functionally graded porous structures

Mechanical properties of porous specimens are much lower than that of dense specimens. This is because true cross-sectional area is extremely lower in the porous specimens. This strength reduction is a main point of disadvantage in the porous materials, and therefore the effective method should be considered for enhancing the strength of porous components. It is well-known in a structural designing of composites that the sandwich structure shows the good performance in specific modulus and specific strength. Then the authors tried to make the multilayered specimens with graded porous sandwich structure. Fig. 8 shows SEM images of the graded porous metals produced by co-sintering the laminated green compacts, which were stacked five plates with various contents of PMMA particles in several sequences, such as type (a) 0, 30, 60, 30, 0vol.% and type (b) 60, 30, 0, 30, 60vol.% with inverse symmetry. It was revealed from these SEM images that the macroscopically graded porous structures revealed and no defects appeared in the interfacial region between each layer.

Fig. 8: Porous graded structures produced by co-sintering laminated green compacts

Fig. 9 shows the bending stress - strain curves and bending modulus of plain porous specimens and graded porous ones. In case of plain porous specimens, the ultimate stresses of specimens with 30 and 60vol.% PMMA particle are very low, and the bending strength and modulus decrease drastically with increasing in fraction of PMMA particle. The behavior can be also confirmed from fracture aspects shown in Fig.10. Brittle fracture occurred due to the rapid fracture propagation in the upper tensile side. On the other hand, either graded porous specimens show a large deformation behavior as with dense 0vol.% PMMA specimen. Definite differences in bending modulus were appeared between type (a) 0-30-60-30-0 and type (b) 60-30-0-30-60 specimens. The bending modulus is higher for type (a) specimens and is lower for type (b) specimens than approximated values. This is because the cracks occurred in the lower skin layer with open cell structure, which was subjected to tensile load, in type (b) specimens.

Thus, definite differences were shown on mechanical properties between plain porous structure and sandwich structure. Therefore it is concluded that this proposed manufacturing method is effective for material design combined in micro scale and macro scale.

Fig. 9: Bending properties of specimens with various fractions of PMMA particles

ID		Plain porous specimens		
		(i) 0	(ii) 30	(iii) 60
Strain				
Near fracture point				
		23.1 % ϵ	11.6 % ϵ	11.6 % ϵ

ID		Graded porous specimens	
		(a) 0-30-60-30-0	(b) 60-30-0-30-60
Strain			
Near fracture point			
		23.1 % ϵ	23.1 % ϵ

Fig.10: Fracture aspects of specimens with various fractions of PMMA particles under bending load

CONCLUSION

The manufacturing methodology of micro-porous metal components by applying a powder space holder method to metal injection moulding process was presented in this study. From the experimental results, it was concluded that the micro-sized metal porous materials could be fabricated with optimizing the fraction of spherical materials for space holding and the conditions of sintering process, and the porosity could be easily controllable and the micro-sized pores were formed homogeneously. Furthermore to advance the manufacturing method proposed, the green compacts with graded content of space holding particles were stacked by hot press moulding and co-sintering process was applied them to form graded porous structure. By comparing the mechanical properties of the materials with plain homogeneous porous specimens and porous graded structure, it was confirmed that desired functionally

graded porous structures can be produced easily and graded porous structures were effective to enhancing the mechanical properties of porous metals. This method would be applicable to injection or extrusion mouldings, then near net shaped production of metal components with complex three-dimensional shapes could be achieved.

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